

ZnO-NiO heterostructure: synthesis, properties and performance as photocatalyst for degradation of organic pollutants

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Abstract

Zinc oxide (ZnO) based materials have attracted much interest in the field of photocatalytic degradation of organic pollutants from waste water. This is due to its high photosensitivity, sustainable band gap, low cost and environmental compatibility [1]. In the present work, ZnO-NiO nanocomposites with different NiO concentrations were synthesized by sonochemical method using zinc acetate ($Zn(CH_3COO)_2$), nickel acetate and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) as starting materials. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis confirms the hexagonal wurtzite phase for ZnO and cubic phase for NiO. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and elemental dot mapping reveals the formation of ZnO-NiO heterostructures with uniform distribution of both components. The photocatalytic performance of the samples was investigated using methylene blue as a model dye under visible (75W Mercury vapor lamp) irradiation. ZnO-NiO heterostructures with different NiO concentration show better photocatalytic activity than individual metal oxides revealing a synergistic effect. This is because of the charge transfer that could happen between the p-type and n-type oxides enhancing the photocatalytic activity [2].

Keywords: Nanocomposite, heterostructure, Photocatalyst, Sonochemical synthesis

References

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